

4Q33 (4QDeut^f) frag. 35 + PAM 43.672 frag. 13

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The two fragments 4Q33 (4QDeut^f) frag. 35 (IAA Plate 317, frag. 14) + PAM 43.672 frag. 13 (IAA Plate 83, frag. 11) should be joined as follows:

Join of IAA Plate 317, frag. 14 (left) and IAA Plate 83, frag. 11 (right) (screenshots)

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-473859>

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-493238>

As a result one may now transcribe 4Q33 frags. 32-35 + PAM 43.672 frag. 13 lines 9-10 as follows (including text from 4Q33 frag. 33 and 34)

וּאֵכְלֶתְּ שֵׁם וְשִׁמְחָה [תּוֹפֵן] נִי יְהוֹה אֲלֵהֶיךָ וְכָתַבְתָּ עַל הָאֲבָנִים	9
מִשֶּׁהוּא [כֹּהֵן] הַלְוִיִּם אֵלַי כֹּל יִשְׂרָאֵל	10

References:

- DJD 14 Eugene Ulrich et al., *Qumran Cave 4, IX: Deuteronomy, Joshua, Judges, Kings*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 14 (Oxford: Clarendon, 1995)
- DJD 33 Dana Pike and Andrew Skinner, *Qumran Cave 4, XXIII: Unidentified Fragments*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 33 (Oxford: Clarendon, 2001)
- IAA Israel Antiquities Authority (used for reference to Plate numbers with scrolls fragments). Fragment numbers are those given by the IAA in The Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library, deadseascrolls.org.il
- PAM Palestine Archaeological Museum (used for references to PAM photographs).